

Quinazolones. Part II. Synthesis of Some Furoquinazolones

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The synthesis of 7-methoxy-2-methyl-2',3-diphenylfuro(4',5' : 5,6)quinazolin-4(3H)-one (IX) and 7-methoxy-2',2,3-triphenylfuro(4',5' : 5,6)quinazolin-4(3H)-one (X) is described.

Chaudhury and co-workers¹⁻³ have recently described the synthesis of a linear as well as some angular 2'-methylfuroquinazolones. In the angular compounds, the furan ring has been developed on a preformed quinazolone at either of the alternative positions 5,6 and 7,8; the 2'-phenyl analogues of which have not been hitherto reported in the literature. This prompted the author to undertake the synthesis of 2'-phenylfuroquinazolones which has been realised and the synthesis of 7-methoxy-2-methyl-2',3-diphenylfuro(4',5' : 5,6)quinazolin-4(3H)-one (IX) and 7-methoxy-2',2,3-triphenylfuro(4',5' : 5,6)quinazolin-4(3H)-one (X) in which the furan ring is fused at the 5,6-position of the quinazolone moiety is the subject matter of this paper.

Out of the several methods available for the synthesis of 2-phenylbenzofurans⁴⁻⁶ the method of Davies and Middleton involving the cyclodehydration of ω -aryloxyacetophenones seems to be most convenient⁶. Adaptation of this procedure for our purpose requires the fusion of a furan ring on preformed quinazolones and therefore 7-methoxy-6-phenacyloxy-2,3-disubstituted quinazolin-4(3H)-ones (III) and (IV) were considered to be the most suitable starting materials, which were secured as follows :

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| I : R = H; | R ₁ = CH ₃ | V : R = H; | R ₁ = CH ₃ |
| II : R = H; | R ₁ = Ph | VI : R = H; | R ₁ = Ph |
| III : R = OCH ₂ COPh; | R ₁ = CH ₃ | VII : R = OCH ₂ COPh; | R ₁ = CH ₃ |
| IV : R = OCH ₂ COPh; | R ₁ = Ph | VIII : R = OCH ₂ COPh; | R ₁ = Ph |

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6. W. Davies and S. Middleton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 822; *Chem. and Ind.*, 1957, 599.

6-Hydroxy-7-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (I)³ and 6-hydroxy-7-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (II)⁷ on treatment with molar proportion of ω -bromoacetophenone in acetone in the presence of potassium carbonate afforded the required intermediate 7-methoxy-6-phenacyloxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (III) and 7-methoxy-6-phenacyloxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (IV) respectively.

Transformation of III and IV to the angular furoquinazolones IX and X were effected by the method of Davies and Middleton⁶ as described below

IX : R = CH₃

X : R = Ph

XI : R = CH₃

XII : R = Ph

According to their observation the cyclodehydration of ω -aryloxyacetophenone by polyphosphoric acid could give β -phenyl or α -phenyl benzofuran depending on the temperature employed, the lower temperature favouring the formation of β -phenyl and higher temperature that of α -phenyl benzofuran. Based on these observations, however, when the cyclodehydration of the phenacyloxyquinazolones III and IV was carried out with polyphosphoric acid identical products were obtained at both the temperatures 80° as well as 132° with a marked lowering in yield below 80°. The products so obtained after the cyclodehydration of III and IV were identified as α -phenylfuroquinazolones 7-methoxy-2-methyl-2',3-diphenylfuro(4',5':5,6)quinazolin-4(3H)-one (IX) and 7-methoxy-2,3-diphenylfuro(4',5':5,6)quinazolin-4(3H)-one (X) respectively as they readily formed complexes with 2,4,7-trinitrofluorenone, which is a characteristic test of α -benzofurans. Isolation of such an exclusive 2'-phenylfuro compound is quite in analogy with the formation of 2-phenyl- α - and β -naphthofurans⁸ by the cyclodehydration of the respective α and β -naphthyl phenacyl ethers under similar conditions. Davies⁶ view can therefore be modified that it is not only the temperature but also the groups present in the aryl nucleus influence the cyclodehydration of ω -aryloxyacetophenones and its subsequent rearrangement, which is also in agreement with the findings of Thomas and Bokadia⁸. A comparison of the UV and IR spectra of the compounds synthesised revealed that the fusion of an α -phenyl furan ring at the 5,6 position of the quinazolone moiety is accompanied with the disappearance of absorption maxima in the near ultra violet region except that for the furan ring (247 m μ) which is developed subsequently as well as a shift in the absorption band at 1710 cm⁻¹ from the normal quinazolone carbonyl frequency (1660 cm⁻¹).

7. S. K. P. Sinha Proceeding papers, Part I.

8. K. K. Thomas and M. M. Bokadia, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **43**, 713.

Unlike III and IV above, the cyclodehydration of the intermediate 4-quinazolones : 8-methoxy-7-phenacyloxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VII) and 8-methoxy-7-phenacyloxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VIII), obtained by the condensation of 7-hydroxy-8-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (V)⁹ and 7-hydroxy-8-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VI)² respectively with ω -bromoacetophenone in acetone in the presence of potassium carbonate, did not furnish the respective linear furoquinazolones. 8-methoxy-2-methyl-2',3-diphenylfuro (4',5' : 6,7)-quinazolin-4(3H)-one (XI) and 8-methoxy-2',2,3-triphenylfuro (4',5' : 6,7)quinazolin-4(3H)-one (XII) under variety of conditions and the unchanged material, having identical spectral data was obtained in each case. The failure of the acid catalysed cyclodehydration could be due to the diminished nucleophilic potential at position 6 owing to their conjugation with the protonated imino group.

Extension of this method to the synthesis of other 2'-phenylfuroquinazolones is in progress and the preparation of isomeric angular (7,8)-2'-phenylfuroquinazolones and linear (6,7)-2'-phenylfuroquinazolones will be published elsewhere.

EXPERIMENTAL*

7-Methoxy-6-phenacyloxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (III) : A mixture of I (1.0 g.; 0.0035 mole), ω -bromoacetophenone (0.7 g.; 0.0035 mole) and anhydrous K_2CO_3 (4 g.) was refluxed in dry acetone (25 ml.) for 4-5 hrs. on steam bath. The solvent (15 ml.) was distilled off, the solution diluted with water and cooled in ice when white solid separated out. It was filtered, washed successively with 10% aq. NaOH and water, dried and crystallised from isopropanol to give III as clusters of colourless long needles (1.2 g.; 90%), m.p. 235-36° (d). (Found : C, 72.2; H, 5.1; N, 6.8. $C_{24}H_{20}O_4N_2$ requires C, 72.0; H, 5.0; N, 7.0%). IR (KBr) 767 cm^{-1} , 1220 cm^{-1} , 1620 cm^{-1} ($= C = N$), 1665 cm^{-1} (quinazolone carbonyl) UV λ_{max} (EtOH) 223 $m\mu$ and 292 $m\mu$.

7-Methoxy-6-phenacyloxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (IV) : The hydroxyquinazolone II (3.44 g.; 0.01 mole), ω -bromoacetophenone (2 g.; 0.01 mole) and anhydrous K_2CO_3 (4 g.) were refluxed in dry acetone for 4-5 hrs. on steam bath. Working as in the previous case afforded the white solid which on crystallisation from dilute ethanol or dilute isopropanol gave IV as colourless needles (2.8 g.; 60%), m.p. 125-26°. (Found : C, 75.0; H, 4.9; N, 6.1. $C_{29}H_{22}O_4N_2$ requires : C, 75.3; H, 4.7; N, 6.0%). IR (KBr) 1620 cm^{-1} ($> C = N$), 1663 cm^{-1} (quinazolone carbonyl) UV λ_{max} (EtOH) 220 $m\mu$ and 302 $m\mu$.

8-Methoxy-7-phenacyloxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VII) : It was prepared as above by refluxing V (2.82 g ; 0.01 mole), ω -bromoacetophenone (2.0 g ; 0.01 mole) in dry acetone (20 ml.) in the presence of anhydrous K_2CO_3 (4 g.) on steam bath for 4-5 hrs. and the product was crystallised from isopropanol to give colourless needles of VII (1 g.; 70%), m.p. 142-43°. (Found : C, 71.8; H, 5.2; N, 7.2. $C_{24}H_{20}O_4N_2$ requires : C, 72.0; H, 5.0; N, 7.0%). IR (KBr) 1610 cm^{-1} ($> C = N$); 1660 cm^{-1} (quinazolone carbonyl) UV λ_{max} (EtOH) 220 $m\mu$ and 300 $m\mu$.

9. S. K. P. Sinha, P. K. Banerjee and D. N. Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 1089.

* All m.p.s. are uncorrected. P.P.A. used was of B.D.H. Laboratory reagent grade. Light petroleum used had b.p. 60-80°.

8-Methoxy-7-phenacyloxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VIII) Following the procedure described for the preparation of III, the hydroxyquinazolone VI (3.44 g.; 0.01 mole) was mixed with ω -bromoacetophenone (2.0 g.; 0.01 mole) and anhydrous K_2CO_3 (4 g.) in dry acetone and the mixture when refluxed on water bath for 4–5 hrs. gave VIII which was crystallised from ethanol to yield colourless needles (2.3 g.; 50%), m.p. 161–62°. (Found : C, 75.5; H, 4.9; N, 6.2. $C_{29}H_{22}O_4N_2$ requires : C, 75.3; H, 4.7; N, 6.0%). IR (KBr) 1610 cm^{-1} ($>C=N$), 1660 cm^{-1} (quinazolone carbonyl) UV λ_{max} (EtOH) 225 $m\mu$ and 303 $m\mu$.

7-Methoxy-2-methyl-2',3-diphenylfuro(4',5' : 5,6)quinazolin-4(3H)-one (IX) : III (4 g.; 0.01 mole) was added in heated PPA at 80° for 20–30 min. and mixed. The mixture was then heated at 80° with occasional stirring for 4 hrs., cooled and poured in ice water. The solid was collected next day, washed with water and crystallised from ethylacetate to give IX as white tiny needles (3.4 g.; 90%), m.p. 137–38°. (Found : C, 75.0; H, 4.6; N, 7.5. $C_{24}H_{18}O_3N_2$ requires : C, 75.3; H, 4.7; N, 7.3%). IR (KBr) 1120 cm^{-1} , 1620 cm^{-1} and 1710 cm^{-1} (quinazoline carbonyl and imino groups) UV λ_{max} (EtOH) 247 $m\mu$.

It yielded an orange red 2,4,7-trinitrofluorenone m.p. 174–75°.

7-Methoxy-2,2',3-triphenylfuro(4',5' : 5,6)quinazolin-4(3H)-one (X) : Cyclodehydration of IV (4.62 g.; 0.01 mole) was carried out at 80° for 4 hrs. in presence of PPA and worked up as in the previous case. The product was crystallised from ethylacetate-light petroleum or ethanol to give X as colourless flakes (2.7 g.; 60%), m.p. 141–42°. (Found : C, 72.2; H, 5.6; N, 14.1. $C_{29}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires : C, 72.0; H, 5.8; N, 13.9%). IR (KBr) 1110 cm^{-1} , 1613 cm^{-1} and 1720 cm^{-1} (quinazoline carbonyl and imino groups) UV λ_{max} (EtOH) 252 $m\mu$.

Its 2,4,7-trinitrofluorenone derivative crystallised as red needles from ethanol m.p. 160–61°.

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